

Phytochemical Investigation of *Parthenium hysterophorous* Linn. An Irritating but Promising Weed

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PARTHENIUM *hysterophorous* Linn. (Compositae), though native to West Indies and Central and Northern America now grows abundantly throughout India. The plant is well known for its irritant properties and dermatitis causing effect. In spite of these, *Parthenium* possesses a number of useful properties. It is reported to be used as a powerful tonic, febrifuge, analgesic in neuralgia, in dysentery and as an agent to stimulate menstrual function¹. An active principle, parthenin², isolated previously from this plant is reported to have anti-cancer properties. Moreover, the plant is highly resistant to all pathogens and insect predators¹.

Petroleum ether extract of dried and powdered whole plant, followed by careful separation through chromatography over silica gel afforded compound A and a sterol, C₂₉H₄₈O, m.p. 155-56°, identified as stigmasterol.

Compound A, C₁₆H₃₂O (M⁺, 240), m.p. 80°, showed characteristic ir absorption bands at 1750 cm⁻¹ (>C=O) and 733, 722 cm⁻¹. Characteristic doublet at 1481 and 1471 cm⁻¹ coupled with the presence of strong peak at m/z 43 in its mass spectrum suggested the presence of *iso*-propyl group in the molecule. Besides the broad signal at δ 1.20 and a triplet around δ 0.90 (3H), the other important characteristic pmr signal is around δ 2.26 (4H, m). Mass spectra of the compound showed besides molecular ion peak at m/z 240 a number of prominent peaks at m/z 43, 57 (base peak), 72, 85, 98, 113 and 127 which can be rationalised fairly well on the basis of the structure (I)

The marc left after the light petroleum ether extract was extracted with chloroform. The concentrate upon chromatographic purification yielded a further crop of stigmasterol from benzene eluate. Further elution with chloroform furnished a compound, C₁₅H₁₈O₄ (M⁺, 262), m.p. 164-66°, identified as parthenin² (m.m.p., co-tlc and mixed ir).

Experimental

All melting points were recorded on a Kofler Block and are uncorrected. The air dried and powdered whole plant (2.50 kg) of *Parthenium hysterophorous* was exhaustively extracted with light petrol (60-80°) in a soxhlet for 24 hr. The solvent was removed by distillation and the crude blackish residue (20 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (450 g) using solvents of increasing polarity as eluents. Light petrol (60-80°)-benzene (3 : 1) eluates afforded compound A, which was crystallised from acetone as granular white solid, C₁₆H₃₂O (M⁺, 240), m.p. 80°. (Found : C, 79.8 ; H, 12.9. C₁₆H₃₂O requires C, 80.0 ; H, 13.3%).

Benzene eluates yielded white crystalline substance, m.p. 155-56° which was identified as stigmasterol.

The marc left after light petrol extract was then exhaustively extracted with benzene. The extract was concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel when a further crop of stigmasterol migrated out with benzene. Chloroform fractions yielded white semi solid residue (0.70 g) which upon rechromatography over silica gel furnished white solid which was crystallised from light petrol-benzene mixture as needles. The compound, C₁₅H₁₈O₄ (M⁺, 262), m.p. 164-65° was identified as parthenin². (Found : C, 68.54 ; H, 6.70. C₁₅H₁₈O₄ requires C, 68.70 ; H, 6.83%).

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References

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Chemical Examination of *Scirpus tuberosus* (Cyperaceae)†

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MEDICINAL uses attributed to several members of the natural order Cyperaceae^{1,2} attracted our attention to *Scirpus tuberosus*, an aquatic plant

† Full details of the isolation and identification of the compounds are available on request.